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Title: HARMONY WITHIN: NURTURING MARIANS' LIVED EXPERIENCES ON BELONGINGNESS AND PEACE

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Abstract

Fostering sense of belonging and peace in school is fundamental in order to create a safe and supportive learning environment, nurture respect, empathy and fairness among students, and address issues on bullying, discrimination, violence, and inequity. Students who feel a strong sense of belonging to their academic community are more likely to engage in academic activities, seek help when needed, and persist in their educational goals (Goodenow & Grady, 2018). The sense of belonging in universities is closely linked to students' sense of peace and well-being on campus. As stated in the 2030 Agenda set by the United Nations for Sustainable Development, institutions should be strengthened in promoting peaceful, inclusive and just societies (SDG #16). The studies of Wilson and Lipsey (2018); Jones, Kljakovic, and Taylor (2018); Palaganas and Dela Cruz (2018) found that schools implementing restorative practices experienced reductions in suspension rates, improvements in school climate and increased feelings of safety among students. However, notable gaps on this area were identified such as perspectives and engagement of students themselves in shaping peace initiatives. This study aimed to determine the sense of belongingness among Marians in relation to their sex and cultural affiliations, explore their lived experiences on peace in the university. The study employed quantitative-qualitative approach, specifically descriptive design. A survey instrument was used to determine the level of sense of belongingness of the Marians. To explore the lived experiences of the respondents on peace, interview was conducted. Focus group discussion (FGD) was used to delve deeply into the students' lived experiences and surface insights and perspectives that may not have been captured in the survey. The findings were used as basis in the Project PEACE HUB: Promoting Empathy, Acceptance, and Civic Engagement by Harnessing Unity and Building Belongingness among Marians.

Keywords: *Involvement, Promoting Empathy, Social acceptance, Valued competence*

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Introduction

The formative period for students' identity development takes place in the university and a sense of belonging plays a critical role in this process. As stated in the study of Espinosa (2015), the university provides students with a supportive environment to explore their interests, values, and aspirations, leading to greater self-confidence and self-awareness. There has been a growing recognition that exists on the critical role that sense of belonging plays in the academic success, persistence, and overall well-being of students in university settings. As shown in the study of Goodenow & Grady (2018), students who feel a strong sense of belonging to their academic community are more likely to engage in academic activities, seek help when needed, and persist in their educational goals. A sense of belonging is a crucial factor in students' decision to persist in their studies and remain enrolled in university. Thus, students who feel disconnected from their academic community are at greater risk of dropping out or transferring to another institution (Strayhorn, 2019).

However, there are challenges that affect the sense of belonging among students. The transition to university life can be a critical period for students' sense of belonging, with many experiencing feelings of loneliness and isolation. Moreover, the study of Espinosa (2015) stated that institutions with diverse student populations may face challenges in fostering a sense of belonging among all students, particularly those from underrepresented or marginalized groups. Similarly, the study of Mayhew et al. (2016) found that students who struggle to integrate socially within their academic community may experience a lack of belonging. This can be exacerbated by factors such as commuter status, part-time enrollment, or feeling disconnected from campus activities.

The sense of belonging in universities is closely linked to students' sense of peace and well-being on campus. When students feel a strong connection to their academic community, they experience a greater sense of security, support, and contentment. Sense of peace among university students is important because it directly influences their overall well-being, academic performance, and satisfaction with their university experience. Research indicates that students who feel a strong sense of belonging experience lower levels of stress and anxiety (Ostrove & Long, 2018). They are more likely to view challenges as manageable and seek out social support during times of difficulty, which promotes a sense of peace and resilience in the face of academic and personal stressors.

A sense of peace contributes to students' emotional well-being by reducing stress, anxiety, and depression. As shown in the study of Rooney et al. (2019), university students who experience high levels of peace report greater life satisfaction and lower levels of psychological distress. Moreover, Sinha et al. (2016) found that students who feel a sense of peace are better able to concentrate, focus, and engage in their academic work. They are more likely to adopt effective study habits, manage their time efficiently, and perform well in exams and assignments. Similarly, a sense of peace can enhance students' sense of belongingness and commitment to their academic goals, thereby increasing retention and persistence rates. Students who feel at peace with themselves and their environment are more likely to stay enrolled and graduate from university (Boyd et al., 2017). In addition, the study of Heckman et al. (2018) found that there is a close link between peace of mind and

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physical health. University students who experience higher levels of peace exhibit better health outcomes. They are less likely to engage in risky behaviors and more inclined to adopt healthy lifestyle practices.

Research on the sense of belonging and peace among students has made significant strides in recent years, but there are still gaps that warrant further investigation. While some studies have explored the sense of belonging among specific student populations (e.g., racial minorities, first-generation students), there is a need for research that examines how multiple intersecting identities (e.g., race, gender, socioeconomic status) influence students' sense of belonging. As stated in the study of Chavous et al. (2015), studies in diverse cultural contexts are needed to understand how sense of belonging operates. While some studies have examined interventions aimed at enhancing students' sense of belonging, there is limited research on how students navigate or process their lived experiences on the sense of belonging and peace in the university.

Related Studies

Studies have been conducted to determine the university students' sense of belongingness when grouped according to sex. The study of Riegler-Crumb et al. (2017) found that female students in STEM fields reported lower levels of belongingness compared to their male counterparts. Female students often faced gender stereotypes, isolation, and lack of representation, which negatively impacted their sense of belongingness in these male-dominated fields. This was contradicted by the study of Johnson et al. (2017) which found that female students reported higher levels of social belongingness compared to male students. Female students tended to form stronger social connections, participate in more campus activities, and seek out supportive relationships with peers and faculty, leading to a greater sense of belongingness during their transition to university. However, the study of Goodenow & Grady (2018) found that while there were no significant gender differences in overall sense of belongingness, the factors influencing belongingness varied between male and female students. For example, male students placed greater importance on academic achievement and recognition, while female students emphasized interpersonal relationships and social support as key contributors to their sense of belongingness.

Several research works have also been conducted to determine the university students' sense of belongingness when grouped according to cultural affiliation. The study

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conducted by Smith et al. (2016) found that ethnic minority students often experienced lower levels of belongingness compared to their majority counterparts. Factors such as cultural isolation, discrimination, and lack of representation contributed to feelings of alienation and reduced sense of belongingness among ethnic minority students. Similarly, the study made by Steinhauer et al. (2017) found that indigenous students often faced cultural marginalization and invisibility within university settings, leading to feelings of isolation and disconnection from their academic community. Culturally relevant support services, mentorship programs, and initiatives to promote indigenous cultural identity were identified as important factors in fostering a sense of belongingness among indigenous students.

Research works on the university students' sense of peace showed a significant positive correlation between mindfulness practices and students' reported levels of peace of mind. Students who engaged in regular mindfulness exercises reported lower levels of stress and greater feelings of calmness and contentment (Zhang et al., 2018). Similarly, MacLean et al. (2016) found that participation in the meditation program was associated with improvements in students' sense of peace, stress reduction, and overall psychological well-being. Regular meditation practice was linked to greater feelings of calmness, clarity, and inner peace among university students. In addition, there is a positive association between spiritual well-being and peace of mind. Students who reported higher levels of spiritual well-being, including feelings of connectedness, purpose, and meaning, also reported greater overall peace of mind (Musa et al., 2017). On the other had, the study of Lee et al. (2015) found that students who spent time in green spaces on campus reported higher levels of peace and tranquility compared to those who did not. Access to nature and greenery was associated with reduced stress levels and improved overall well-being among university students. The study of Johnson & Johnson (2015) investigated the impact of implementing collaborative and cooperative learning strategies on promoting peace and reducing conflict in university classrooms. The findings suggested that fostering positive interdependence, mutual respect, and active participation among students contributed to a more peaceful and supportive learning environment. In addition, the study of Al-Haj & Khamis (2017) explored strategies and interventions for managing diversity and promoting peaceful coexistence among students from different cultural, religious, and social backgrounds on university campuses. The findings highlighted the importance of creating inclusive policies, fostering intercultural dialogue, and providing training and support for faculty and staff to address conflicts and promote understanding.

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Theoretical Framework

Self-Determination Theory (SDT), developed by Deci and Ryan (1985), offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the psychological needs underlying human motivation, including the sense of belonging. SDT posits that individuals are driven by three fundamental psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. These needs are essential for fostering intrinsic motivation, well-being, and optimal functioning. Autonomy refers to the need to feel volitional and self-directed in one's actions. In the context of sense of belonging, autonomy entails having the freedom to express one's true self, make choices aligned with personal values, and engage in behaviors that reflect authentic identity. When individuals feel autonomy-supportive environments where their choices and perspectives are respected, they are more likely to develop a sense of belongingness. For example, universities can promote autonomy by offering students opportunities for self-expression, involvement in decision-making processes, and autonomy-supportive teaching practices. Competence refers to the need to feel effective and capable in one's interactions and pursuits. In the context of sense of belonging, competence involves feeling proficient and valued within social and academic contexts. When individuals perceive themselves as competent members of their academic community, they are more likely to develop a sense of belongingness. Universities can foster competence by providing students with meaningful challenges, opportunities for skill development, and supportive feedback that validates their abilities and contributions. Relatedness refers to the need to feel connected and cared for by others. In the context of sense of belonging, relatedness encompasses feeling connected to peers, faculty, and the broader university community. When individuals experience supportive relationships and a sense of belongingness within their social networks, they are more likely to thrive academically and emotionally. Universities can promote relatedness by creating inclusive and supportive environments, fostering interpersonal connections through peer support programs, mentorship initiatives, and extracurricular activities, and providing avenues for social interaction and collaboration. SDT emphasizes that meeting these psychological needs is essential for fostering intrinsic motivation, psychological well-being, and optimal functioning. When individuals' autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs are satisfied, they are more likely to experience a deep sense of belongingness and engagement in their academic pursuits and social interactions. As such, universities can leverage SDT as a framework for designing interventions and initiatives aimed at enhancing students' sense of belongingness and creating inclusive and supportive campus

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environments. These efforts can ultimately contribute to students' academic success, well-being, and overall satisfaction with their university experience.

Conflict resolution and peace studies provide a robust theoretical framework for understanding and cultivating a sense of peace. This framework encompasses interdisciplinary perspectives from psychology, sociology, political science, and international relations, offering insights into the causes of conflict, dynamics of peacebuilding, and promotion of positive relationships. Peace studies highlight the interconnectedness of peacebuilding efforts at multiple levels, including individual, interpersonal, societal, and global. Peacebuilding initiatives seek to address underlying causes of conflict, promote social justice, and foster positive relationships among diverse groups. Reconciliation processes aim to heal past wounds, promote forgiveness, and build sustainable peace based on principles of equity, inclusion, and human rights. In the context of university settings, peacebuilding strategies aim to promote a culture of peace, understanding, and cooperation among students, faculty, and staff. These strategies draw on principles of conflict resolution, intergroup dialogue, and community engagement to address sources of tension, foster positive relationships, and create inclusive and supportive environments. One example of these strategies is Interfaith and Intercultural Dialogue which promote understanding and appreciation of diverse religious and cultural perspectives. These dialogues provide opportunities for students, faculty, and staff from different backgrounds to engage in open and respectful conversations, share experiences, and build bridges of understanding. Another strategy is Peer Mediation Programs wherein trained student mediators facilitate constructive dialogue and conflict resolution among their peers. Peer mediation offers a confidential and informal process for resolving disputes, addressing interpersonal conflicts, and restoring relationships within the university community. Community Service and Civic Engagement is another good strategy that connects students with local communities and address social issues through collaborative action. Engaging in service projects and community-based learning opportunities fosters empathy, social responsibility, and a sense of shared purpose among students, contributing to a culture of peace and social justice.

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Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Figure 1. *Research Paradigm*

This study aimed to determine the level of sense of belongingness of the Marian students in general and when grouped according to sex and cultural affiliation. Moreover, this study also aimed to bring forth the lived experiences of the Marian students in terms of sense of peace in the university.

The findings of the study served as basis in drafting the Project PEACE HUB: Promoting Empathy, Acceptance, and Civic Engagement by Harnessing Unity and Building Belongingness among Marians. It is a project consisting of seminars, trainings, and workshops that will foster dialogue among Marians of diverse cultural backgrounds, building cohesive and resilient student community, and promoting collaboration and mutual understanding.

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Statement of the Problem

Generally, this study aimed to determine the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness, the ways by which they process their sense of belongingness, their lived experiences on sense of peace, and the challenges they have experiences in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university. This study was conducted at Saint Mary's University within the school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study aimed to provide answers on the following questions:

1. What is the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness at the university in general and when grouped according to:
 - a. gender
 - b. cultural affiliation
2. Is there significant difference in the Marian students' sense of belongingness when grouped according to profile variables?
3. What are the Marian students' lived experiences on sense of peace at the university?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the Marian students in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university?

Hypothesis of the Study

There is no significant difference in the level of sense of belongingness among Marian students when grouped according to sex and cultural affiliation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to determine the sense of belongingness among Marians, explore their lived experiences on belongingness and peace in the university, and surface activities and/or programs on belongingness and peace initiatives. According to Ahmad et al. (2019), qualitative research is a naturalistic inquiry method that seeks to profoundly comprehend social phenomena in their natural setting, concentrating on the "why" rather than the "what." The qualitative methodology used was phenomenology to gather and analyze narratives and open-ended observations through interviews and focus groups discussions. Overall, the study included administering questionnaires and conducting interviews and focus group discussions.

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Locale

This study was conducted at Saint Mary's University tertiary campus. Saint Mary's University is a premier CICM Catholic educational institution drawn into communion by the Wisdom of God, dedicated to the integral formation of persons exemplifying excellence, innovation, and passion for Christ's mission. SMU carries on the mission of integral human development by joyfully witnessing to Christ's mission, responsibly taking the lead and participating in community-building, relentlessly manifesting academic, personal and professional excellence, conscientiously strengthening communion, and steadfastly nurturing creativity and physical prowess.

Participants and Sample

There 365 respondents of the study selected through stratified random sampling. Marian students were randomly selected as the respondents of the study since they were expected to have rich experiences in terms of sense and belongingness and peace in the university as warranted by the different number of years they have spent in the university. Research participants benefited from the study as their participation contributed to the advancement of knowledge and understanding in various fields. Participating in this research also helped the respondents gain better understanding of their own experiences, attitudes and behaviors. Their contributions are valuable in determining the sense of belongingness among Marians and explore their lived experiences on belongingness and peace in the university.

Profile of the respondents

Table 2. Profile of the respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Males	84	23
Females	276	75.6
Total	360	98.6
Missing System	5	1.4
Overall Total	365	100

Table 2 shows that among the 365 respondents, 84 were males, 276 were females and there were 5 who did not indicate their sex

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Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of cultural affiliation

Cultural Affiliation	Frequency	Percent
Ilocano	111	30.4
Ifugao	39	10.7
Tagalog	36	9.9
Others (Isinai, Gaddang)	17	0.5
Total	203	55.6
Missing System	162	44.4
Overall Total	365	100

Table 3 shows that, among the 365 respondents, the greatest number were Ilocanos (30.4%) followed by the Ifugaos (39 or 10.7%), the Tagalogs (36 or 9.9%) and other cultural affiliations like the Gaddang and the Isinay consisted of 17 (0.5%). There were 162 respondents who did not disclose their cultural affiliations.

Instrument(s)

This study employed a comprehensive survey instrument adopted from the study of Ahn & Davis (2020) to collect both quantitative data on students' perspectives and experiences and qualitative insights through interviews or focus groups to delve into their lived experiences on sense of belongingness and peace. The research instrument used to determine the sense of belongingness of the Marian students was the Departmental Sense of Belonging and Involvement which was used by Ahn & Davis (2020) in their study entitled Students' Sense of Belonging and their Socio-Economic Status in Higher Education: A Quantitative Approach. The research instrument has a Cronbach alpha of 0.71 which indicates that it is a good fit for the study. The survey consisted of four parts, each serving distinct objectives: Part 1 assessed demographic factors such as sex and cultural affiliations. Part 2 determined whether the Marians' level of sense of belongingness and peace differ when grouped according to the demographic variables. Part 3 analyzed the qualitative components of students' lived experiences on their sense of belongingness and peace in the university.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection approach for this study will consist of three subsections: (1) survey, (2) interviews, (3) Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

(1) Survey was used to gather quantitative data about the studies.

(2) Interviews were conducted to assess qualitative insights about the study.

(3) Focus Group Discussion enabled collective conversations among participants, thereby boosting the qualitative data collection process. It will allowed participants to interact with each other.

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Treatment of Data

To establish the Marians' level of sense of belongingness and peace, the following statistics are supplied for each research problem:

For problem statement 1, frequency and percentage distribution will be used to determine the respondents' sex and cultural affiliation. Furthermore, stratified sampling was used to ensure that the respondents represent a diverse range of demographics.

For problem statement 2, parametric were used to determine the level of sense of belongingness when grouped by sex and cultural affiliations

For problem statement 3, thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes and patterns in students' input about their lived experiences on sense of peace in the university.

Table 1 was used as basis in determining the students' level of sense of belongingness.

Table 1. Scale and Qualitative description

Rating	Scale	Qualitative Description
1	1.00-1.49	Not at all
2	1.50-2.49	Little extent
3	2.50-3.49	Moderate extent
4	3.50-4.00	Great extent

Ethical Considerations

This study was submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMU-REB), Second Floor, Rev. Fr. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines for their approval and monitoring. SMU-REB is chaired by Mr. Jason Arnold L. Maslang (email: reb@smu.edu.ph/mobile: 09177053041).

There is conflict of interest in conducting this study inasmuch as both the researchers and respondents of the study belong to Saint Mary's University.

There is a potential risk of confidentiality breach for data that may be shared during the FGD since information sharing is between researchers and participants and among the participants. The results of this study will be disseminated to the participants inasmuch as the findings of the study will help them gain knowledge about themselves in terms of sense of belongingness as well as they will be provided information about their lived experiences

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on peace in the university. Moreover, the extended abstract of this study will be published in the SMU website.

An Informed Consent Form will be provided to the respondents. The purpose and significance of the study will be discussed with the concerned participants. To secure the respondents' privacy, respondents' codes will be used to label the data instead of using their names. Data collected will be protected by ensuring that access to all confidential and sensitive data will be managed appropriately. After the study is completed and finally bound in a book, all the data will be deleted for good.

This study involves the conduct of interviews and focus group discussion. The schedule to conduct the study will be set within the convenience of the participants. The respondents are selected as participants because they provided rich data for the study. The respondents' participation is voluntary and they could withdraw any time without explanation.

Information and ideas coming from various authors are cited throughout the paper using the APA citation style.

Saint Mary's University is the sole owner of the intellectual property of the study.

Results and Discussion

Table 4. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of valued competence at the university in general*

Valued competence	Mean	Std. Deviation	QD
1. People in our department notice when I am good at something.	2.58	0.751	Moderate
2. Faculty and staff in our department value my opinions.	2.65	0.743	Moderate
3. Most faculty and staff in our department are interested in me	2.16	0.767	Little
4. People in our department know I can do good work.	2.63	0.784	Moderate
5. The instructors in our department give me compliments when I do something good.	2.7	0.804	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.54	0.58	Moderate

Legend: 1.0-1.49 Not at all; 1.50-2.49=Little; 2.50-3.49=Moderate; 3.50-4.0=Great

Table 4 shows the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of valued competence at the university in general. As shown by the overall mean (M=2.54), the respondents manifested moderate level in terms of valued competence. The highest mean indicates that faculty and staff value their opinions whereas the lowest mean indicates that most faculty and staff in their department are interested in them. As stated in the study of Pedler, Willis, & Nieuwoudt (2022), a sense of belonging is important as it incorporates feelings of being valued, included and accepted at university. This suggests that higher

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education students who have a greater sense of belonging tend to have higher motivation, more academic self-confidence, higher levels of academic engagement and higher achievement.

Table 5. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance at the university in general*

Sense of belonging: social acceptance	Mean	Std. Deviation	QD
1. Students in our department help each other to succeed.	3.06	0.739	Moderate
2. I am treated with as much respect as other students.	3.08	0.686	Moderate
3. I have a good relationship with other students in our department.	3.20	0.642	Moderate
3. I have a good relationship with other students in our department.	3.05	1.797	Moderate
5. I feel proud of belonging to our department.	3.17	0.713	Moderate
6. Other students in our department like me the way I am.	2.84	0.731	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.06	0.600	Moderate

Table 5 presents the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance at the university in general. As shown by the overall mean (M=3.06), the level of belongingness in terms of social acceptance was moderate. The highest mean (M=3.20) shows that the respondents have a good relationship with other students in our department whereas the lowest mean (M=2.84) indicated that other students in their department like them the way they are. The study of Haim-Litevsky, Komemi, & Lipskaya-Velikovsky (2023) provides empirical support to the interrelationship between sense of belonging and acceptance, connectedness, and well-being. This implies that when students are accepted and feel a strong sense of belongingness, it leads to greater confidence in their abilities and potentials.

Table 6. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of Involvement in general*

Involvement	Mean	Std. Deviation	QD
During this academic year, it is likely that I will:			
1. participate in undergraduate research (paid or unpaid) in our department.	2.87	0.899	Moderate
2. interact closely with faculty or staff in our department outside of class.	2.53	0.783	Moderate
3. ask for advice from a faculty or staff in our department.who is not my instructor.	2.44	0.915	Moderate
4. attend the office hours of a faculty member in our department. .	2.35	0.907	Moderate

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5. read research papers from a faculty member in our department.	2.34	0.863	Moderate
6. attend a seminar hosted by in our department.	3.06	0.78	Moderate
7. visit the lab of a faculty member in our department.	2.61	0.913	Moderate
8. join a related student group or club at Saint Mary's University	2.57	0.963	Moderate
9. participate in related volunteer work not connected to research (e.g., clean up beaches or volunteer in a state park).	2.75	0.817	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.61	0.589	Moderate

Table 6 presents the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of Involvement in general. The overall mean (M=2.61) shows that the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of Involvement is to a moderate extent. The highest mean (M=3.06) indicated they will attend a seminar hosted by their department to a moderate level whereas the lowest mean (M=2.34) showed they will read research papers from a faculty member in our department. In the study of Gillen-O'Neel (2021), sense of belonging was associated with all types of student involvement at both the person and the daily levels. At the person level, students with a higher sense of belonging than their peers tended to also have higher emotional and behavioral involvement. This findings suggest that sense of belonging is an important resource for maintaining student involvement and engagement among all students.

Table 7. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of valued competence when grouped according to sex*

Valued competence	sex	Mean	SD	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
1. People in our department notice when I am good at something	Male	2.69	0.711	1.538	0.216	1.468	358	0.143
	Female	2.55	0.754			1.515	144.379	0.132
2. Faculty and staff in our department value my opinions	Male	2.68	0.731	0.776	0.379	0.402	358	0.688
	Female	2.64	0.747			0.407	139.932	0.685
3. Most faculty and staff in our department are interested in me	Male	2.21	0.793	0.614	0.434	0.791	356	0.429
	Female	2.14	0.758			0.773	132.85	0.441
4. People in our department know I can do good work.	Male	2.69	0.84	0.742	0.39	0.722	357	0.471
	Female	2.62	0.766			0.687	125.778	0.493
5. The instructors in our department give me compliments when I do something good.	Male	2.7	0.861	1.346	0.247	0.103	358	0.918
	Female	2.69	0.788			0.098	128.192	0.922
Overall Mean	Male	2.59	0.599	0.013	0.91	0.878	358	0.381
	Female	2.52	0.588			0.869	135.239	0.386

Table 7 shows the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of valued competence when grouped according to sex. The *t* test showed that there is no significant difference in the Marian's level of valued competence when grouped according to

sex. This means that the level of belongingness of the Marian students when grouped according to sex is statistically the same.

Table 8. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance when grouped according to sex*

	sex	Mean	SD	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
1. Students in our department help each other to succeed.	Male	3.1	0.722	0.006	0.939	0.406	358	0.685
	Female	3.06	0.741			0.412	140.46	0.681
2. I am treated with as much respect as other students.	Male	3.04	0.685	1.079	0.3	0.684	358	0.494
	Female	3.09	0.686			0.685	137.67	0.494
3. I have a good relationship with other students in our department.	Male	3.23	0.588	0.824	0.365	0.337	358	0.736
	Female	3.2	0.655			0.357	151.04	0.721
4. I can really be myself in our department.	Male	3.01	0.784	0.54	0.463	0.204	358	0.838
	Female	3.06	2.019			-0.31	339.21	0.757
5. I feel proud of belonging to our department.	Male	3.13	0.741	0.019	0.889	0.525	358	0.6
	Female	3.18	0.704			-0.51	131.88	0.611
6. Other students in our department like me the way I am.	Male	2.87	0.803	0.938	0.333	0.397	357	0.691
	Female	2.83	0.71			0.372	125.23	0.71
OMSB	Male	3.061	0.528	0.72	0.397	0.111	358	0.912
	Female	3.069	0.621			0.121	159.08	0.904

Table 8 shows the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance when grouped according to sex. The *t* test showed that there is no significant difference in the Marians' level of valued competence when grouped according to sex. This means that the level of belongingness of the Marian students when grouped according to sex is statistically the same. However, in the study of Edwards, Barthelemy, & Frey (2021), students' social belonging has been shown to differ across demographics, such as gender.

Table 9. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of involvement when grouped according to sex*

	sex	Mean	SD	F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
1. participate in undergraduate research (paid or unpaid) in our department	Male	2.71	0.964	3.917	0.049	1.781	358	0.076
	Female	2.91	0.874			-1.69	127.278	0.093
2. interact closely with faculty or staff in our department outside of class.	Male	2.58	0.867	2.361	0.125	0.895	358	0.371
	Female	2.5	0.751			0.829	123.249	0.409
3. ask for advice from a faculty or staff in our department who is not my instructor.	Male	2.49	1.012	4.321	0.038	0.644	357	0.52
	Female	2.41	0.885			0.6	124.289	0.55
4. attend the office hours of a faculty member in our department. .	Male	2.55	0.924	0.602	0.438	2.415	357	0.016
	Female	2.28	0.894			2.373	133.977	0.019
5. read research papers from a faculty member in our department.	Male	2.44	0.896	1.004	0.317	1.297	357	0.196
	Female	2.3	0.846			1.257	131.315	0.211
6. attend a seminar hosted by in our department.	Male	2.99	0.848	1.649	0.2	-0.94	357	0.348
	Female	3.08	0.759			-	124.056	0.378
7. visit the lab of a faculty member in our department.	Male	2.71	0.858	2.9	0.089	1.262	357	0.208
	Female	2.57	0.927			1.315	147.007	0.191
8. join a related student group or club at Saint Mary's University	Male	2.62	0.968	0	0.991	0.692	358	0.49
	Female	2.54	0.958			0.688	136.235	0.493
9. participate in related volunteer work not connected to research (e.g., clean up beaches or volunteer in a state park).	Male	2.69	0.791	0.026	0.872	0.686	357	0.493
	Female	2.76	0.82			-	141.756	0.486
OMIN	Male	2.642	0.653	3.37	0.067	0.64	358	0.522
	Female	2.59	0.561			0.591	122.629	0.556

Table 9 shows the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of involvement when grouped according to sex. The *t* test yielded significant difference (p value = 0.16) on the statement indicating their attendance to the office hours of a faculty member in their department. The male respondents have higher mean values than the females and the difference is significant. The *t* test yielded significant difference (p value = 0.16) on the statement indicating their attendance to the office hours of a faculty member in their department. The male respondents have higher mean values than the females and the difference is significant. Similarly, the study of Verbree, van Der Schaaf, Wijngaards-de Meij,

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& Dilaver (2025) showed that male students felt more comfortable in the classroom and students with disabilities experienced less sense of belonging and authenticity than their peers.

In terms of the other statements, there is no significant difference in the Marians' level of involvement when grouped according to sex.

Table 10. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness at the university in terms of valued competence when grouped according to cultural affiliation*

ANOVA		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. People in our department notice when I am good at something.	Between Groups	5.658	5	1.132	1.921	0.092
	Within Groups	116.057	197	0.589		
	Total	121.714	202			
2. Faculty and staff in our department value my opinions.	Between Groups	2.23	5	0.446	0.771	0.572
	Within Groups	113.957	197	0.578		
	Total	116.187	202			
3. Most faculty and staff in our department are interested in me	Between Groups	1.168	5	0.234	0.372	0.868
	Within Groups	123.797	197	0.628		
	Total	124.966	202			
4. People in our department know I can do good work.	Between Groups	6.199	5	1.24	1.88	0.099
	Within Groups	129.232	196	0.659		
	Total	135.431	201			
5. The instructors in our department give me compliments when I do something good.	Between Groups	1.401	5	0.28	0.444	0.818
	Within Groups	124.422	197	0.632		
	Total	125.823	202			
OMV5	Between Groups	1.591	5	0.318	0.862	0.507
	Within Groups	72.722	197	0.369		
	Total	74.313	202			

Table 10 presents the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness at the university in terms of valued competence when grouped according to cultural affiliation. . The One Way ANOVA test showed that there is no significant difference in the Marians' level of valued competence when grouped according to cultural affiliation. This means that the level of belongingness of the Marian students when grouped according to cultural affiliation is statistically the same. However, this finding is negated in the study of Sung & Gounko (2023) which revealed that cultural affiliation significantly contributed to the social and academic integration of the participants within their new institutional and social milieu. By cultivating a sense of belonging, it aided the participants in overcoming initial hurdles, such as isolation and acknowledging their status as minorities. Cultural affiliation played a crucial role in providing spaces for cultural

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affirmation, championing diversity, facilitating social inclusion, and nurturing a sense of belonging.

Table 11. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance when grouped according to cultural affiliation*

Social acceptance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. Students in our department help each other to succeed.	Between Groups	3.034	5	0.607	1.113	0.355
	Within Groups	107.37	197	0.545		
	Total	110.404	202			
2. I am treated with as much respect as other students.	Between Groups	0.95	5	0.19	0.442	0.819
	Within Groups	84.685	197	0.43		
	Total	85.635	202			
3. I have a good relationship with other students in our department.	Between Groups	1.172	5	0.234	0.545	0.742
	Within Groups	84.72	197	0.43		
	Total	85.892	202			
4. I can really be myself in our department.	Between Groups	0.803	5	0.161	0.282	0.923
	Within Groups	112.192	197	0.57		
	Total	112.995	202			
5. I feel proud of belonging to our department.	Between Groups	0.982	5	0.196	0.396	0.851
	Within Groups	97.737	197	0.496		
	Total	98.719	202			
6. Other students in our department like me the way I am.	Between Groups	2.456	5	0.491	0.944	0.453
	Within Groups	101.926	196	0.52		
	Total	104.381	201			
Overall Mean	Between Groups	0.846	5	0.169	0.637	0.672
	Within Groups	52.279	197	0.265		
	Total	53.125	202			

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Table 11 shows the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance when grouped according to cultural affiliation. The One Way ANOVA showed that there is no significant difference in the Marians' level of sense of belongingness in terms of social acceptance when grouped according to cultural affiliation. This means that the level of belongingness of the Marian students when grouped according to cultural affiliation is statistically the same. However, this was negated in the study of Allen Jr, Belton, Berman, Dilg & Arroyo (2022) which found that the participants in the study consistently touched upon their experiences with belonging in relation to their respective identities and cultural affiliation. Furthermore, participants also shared positive experiences that highlight the necessity of organizations and councils to support students who may belong to minority groups.

Table 12. *Level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of involvement when grouped according to cultural affiliation*

Involvement		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. participate in undergraduate research (paid or unpaid) in our department.	Between Groups	1.926	5	0.385	0.459	0.807
	Within Groups	165.483	197	0.84		
	Total	167.409	202			
2. interact closely with faculty or staff in our department outside of class.	Between Groups	1.779	5	0.356	0.614	0.689
	Within Groups	114.201	197	0.58		
	Total	115.98	202			
3. ask for advice from a faculty or staff in our department who is not my instructor.	Between Groups	0.991	5	0.198	0.244	0.942
	Within Groups	159.758	197	0.811		
	Total	160.749	202			
4. attend the office hours of a faculty member in our department. .	Between Groups	4.185	5	0.837	0.976	0.434
	Within Groups	168.132	196	0.858		
	Total	172.317	201			
5. read research papers from a faculty member in our department.	Between Groups	1.315	5	0.263	0.353	0.88
	Within Groups	145.917	196	0.744		

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	Total	147.233	201			
6. attend a seminar hosted by in our department.	Between Groups	0.395	5	0.079	0.139	0.983
	Within Groups	112.009	197	0.569		
	Total	112.404	202			
7. visit the lab of a faculty member in our department.	Between Groups	6.573	5	1.315	1.576	0.168
	Within Groups	163.472	196	0.834		
	Total	170.045	201			
8. join a related student group or club at Saint Mary's University	Between Groups	4.695	5	0.939	1.019	0.408
	Within Groups	181.561	197	0.922		
	Total	186.256	202			
9. participate in related volunteer work not connected to research (e.g., clean up beaches or volunteer in a state park).	Between Groups	2.701	5	0.54	0.834	0.527
	Within Groups	127.555	197	0.647		
	Total	130.256	202			
Overall Mean	Between Groups	0.529	5	0.106	0.339	0.889
	Within Groups	61.578	197	0.313		
	Total	62.107	202			

Table 12 presents the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness in terms of involvement when grouped according to cultural affiliation. The One Way ANOVA showed that there is no significant difference in the Marians' level of involvement when grouped according to cultural affiliation. This means that the level of belongingness of the Marian students when grouped according to cultural affiliation is statically the same. However, this finding is negated in the study of Verbree, van Der Schaaf, Wijngaards-de Meij, & Dilaver (2025) which found that being part of multiple minority groups impaired aspects of students' sense of belongingness.

Marians' lived experiences of sense of belongingness and peace in the university

The sense of belongingness is one of the significant needs that motivate human behavior, as indicated in Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs. The hierarchy of needs is

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usually portrayed as a pyramid, with more basic needs at the base and more complex needs near the peak. The need for love and belonging lie at the pyramid's center as part of social needs. In the context of active and energetic environment of a university, the importance of belonging and peace of mind are paramount in overall wellbeing and success. Students who feel like they belong are more likely to engage in campus, seek support when needed and persist in their studies. A strong sense of belonging significantly contributes to inner peace and overall wellbeing. Students' notion of peace are diverse and multifaceted, shaped by individual experiences, cultural backgrounds. and current life circumstances.

The interview surfaced the following common themes:

1. Inner calm and Well-being. Inner calm and well-being are interconnected states reflecting a sense of peace, contentment and overall health. Students associate peace with a state of inner calm and wellbeing. Inner calm and well-being reflect a positive state characterized by key elements such as emotional regulation, self-awareness, and purpose of meaning. As expressed by Annie, *"Personally, peace means calmness. When I am at peace, I am mentally, physically, and spiritually calm, and in this way, I can prevent or overcome the chaos that happens or will happen around me"*. Also, Beth stated, *"The term peace means to me is like a feeling of lightness in everyday line. Waking up in the morning without worries, living like you own something good that others can't"*. Cathy also remarked, *"Peace is always accompanied by kindness so cultivating it within could help me become a person whose aim is to achieve and it would flow naturally around people."* Also, Maria expressed, *"Peace brings so much in this world. Thus, sense of peace contributes to my own well-being allowing to embrace the differences of others. Meditation and prayer time are the best practices to maintain inner peace"*.

2. Personal fulfillment and purpose. Personal fulfillment refers to a sense of satisfaction and happiness derived from one's life experiences and accomplishments. It is about feeling content and satisfied with the choices one has made and the life one is living for. Purpose refers to a meaning or direction in life. It is about having a reason for being and a sense of contribution to something larger than one's self. For some students, peace is linked to a sense of purpose and fulfillment As Dina remarked, *"In my daily experience around campus, I feel safe and secured knowing that while being able to learn, I am also surrounded by my friends and I feel peace with it. I start of course by bringing peace to myself first because how can you give peace when you are not even at peace"*.

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3. Social Harmony and Justice. Social harmony and justice are crucial for well-functioning and equitable society. Social harmony emphasizes peaceful coexistence and cooperation whereas social justice focuses on fairness, equity and the elimination of discrimination. Some students connect peace with broader societal concepts as expressed by Jasmine, *"I incorporate my peace in my daily living in campus by doing what I do without hesitation and without disobeying the rules and policies of the university. I create a peaceful environment at the university in a way of coordinating myself to activities that can help the peace."*

Incorporation of peace into one's daily interactions and experiences in campus

1. Self-reflection. Self-reflection is a process of consciously examining one's thoughts, feelings, behaviors and experiences to gain a deeper understanding of oneself. This is expressed in the statement of Jane who said, *"I incorporate peace in my daily interactions and experience through showing to those I encounter. When I do immediately all my "to do list" for a day without procrastinating so I can feel peace afterwards"*. Similarly, Kate mentioned, *"By minding my own business always. What I do is to really focus on myself and not let other people's opinion sway my thoughts. Through this, I become calm and composed, and full of confidence that radiates from within"*.

2. Empathy and compassion. Empathy and compassion play crucial roles in fostering positive relationships and building a more humane society. Empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others. Compassion involves a feeling of concern and a desire to alleviate the suffering. These are expressed by Tina who remarked, *"By being warm and friendly with everyone I meet on campus. By greeting those I come close to, making them feel welcome, and helping out those in need. I can also incorporate peace by showing that the campus is a safe space where there is no judgement. I incorporate my peace by being friendly as I can be. Similarly, Fiona expressed, "By bringing more people comfort. I become comfortable as well. I see having a very light environment. I incorporate peace in my daily life in the campus by always showing a positive attitude and always smiling to other people. To greet and smile the teachers and being friendly with other students as these creates positive and peaceful environment. I try to always be positive and not cause other people burden"*

3. Respectful communication. Respectful communication is about creating a safe and inclusive environment where everyone feels valued and respected. By cultivating respectful communication skills, we can build stronger relationships, foster collaboration and resolve conflicts more effectively. These were expressed in the statements of Yuri who mentioned, *"By being friendly and kind to others. By simply complementing them and making them feel"*

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that they belong to the campus. By choosing the right words to say in all situations.” Moreover, Leila remarked, “ I incorporate peace by not overthinking every single interaction with people. I treat them with respect and I converse with them enthusiastically. Also, I do my best to show respect to other at all times to avoid creating conflicts”.

Creation of a peaceful environment at the university

1. Open communication. Open communication is characterized by transparency, honesty and a willingness to share openly and honestly. Effective open communication is crucial to building strong relationships, fostering collaboration and achieving shared goals. These were shown in the statements of Maya who said, *“I create a peaceful environment for myself and the people around me. By interacting with people openly, not just showing fake face for people to like me. This way I become more comfortable in school. Nena corroborated these statements when she commented, “By being friendly and kind to others. By choosing the right words in all situations and by making them feel that they belong and are seen, heard, and accepted.*

2. Shared values. Shared values are the principles, beliefs and ideals that are commonly held and embraced by a group of people. Shared values guide decision making, shape behavior and influence the culture of a group. These statements were corroborated by Kiel who mentioned, *“Most of the time, what I really do is to respect other people’s personal space so as not to distract them with whatever they are doing. I try to follow rules and not cause other people burden. Sharing seats with other students in common area in the campus just like in canteens and patio. Maintaining cleanliness and proper waste disposal”.* Similarly, Daniel commented, *“By avoiding negativity or the things that could make me react negatively. I create a peaceful environment by maintaining healthy discussions with my peers and avoiding “chismis”. I create a peaceful environment at the university by abiding/following the university rules, whether it is about the proper dress code or some other rules. I also practice being respectful to other people and always practicing CHSF wherever I go.”* Suzette also remarked, *“By not being involve to any conflicts with my fellow students as well as to any instructors and school admins. By minding my own business always so the others can do the same too to me. And by being patient and understanding to others”.*

3. Leadership commitment. Leadership commitment is the unwavering dedication and resolve demonstrated by leaders to achieve a shared vision or goal. Effective leadership commitment is crucial in fostering team cohesion and inspiring others to follow. These are manifested in Shawn’s statements who commented, *“By always looking for situations that may result in conflicts and trying to solve the problem with peaceful means before it goes out of hand. Differences in opinions should be listened to and understood so that no one would be left out to create a peaceful environment.* Moreover, John stated, *“To create a peaceful environment at the university, I always try to be approachable as I can so that other people, especially those in need will not hesitate to ask for help.*

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Challenges encountered by the Marian students in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university

University students often face significant challenges in fostering a sense of belongingness and peace within their campus environment. These challenges can stem from various sources, impacting their academic performance, mental health, and overall well-being.

Academic pressures and competition. The demanding academic environment, couple with intense competition for grades and opportunities can create a stressful atmosphere. Students may feel isolated and pressures to succeed, hindering their ability to connect with peers and cultivate a sense of belonging. This was affirmed in the verbatim responses of the students. Annie mentioned, "I feel pressured to constantly compare myself to my friends that's why I feel inferior and inadequate". Similarly, Beth stated, "I struggle to balance the demands of my parents to pass my subjects and my need to maintain my mental and emotional well-being". Moreover, Cathy stated, "I find it difficult to build genuine connections with my peers".

Social isolation and loneliness. Transitioning to university life can be isolating for many students especially those who come from far towns and provinces and those who have not made friends in the university. Difficulties in making friends, navigating social dynamics, and overcoming feelings of loneliness can significantly impact their sense of belonging and overall well-being. This is affirmed by Diana, "I often feel alone, even if I am with my classmates". This was corroborated by Menchie who remarked, "I find it difficult to make and maintain friendships". Moreover, Eva commented, "I find it difficult to participate in social activities because of my fear of rejection".

Mental health concerns. Stress, anxiety and depression are prevalent among university students. These mental health challenges can exacerbate feelings of isolation and loneliness, making it difficult for students to connect with others and build a sense of community. Lack of access to adequate mental health support further aggravate these issues. As remarked my Fely, "I have been feeling down and hopeless for some time now". Similarly, Beverly mentioned, "I am struggling with panic attacks". Also, Girl stated, "I feel anxious and I cannot concentrate".

Bullying and harassment. Experiences of bullying, harassment, or cyberbullying can severely undermine a student's sense of safety and belonging. These negative experiences can lead to social isolation, anxiety, and depression impacting their academic performance and well-being. This is affirmed by Tina who stated, "I have been bullied by my classmates and I feel unsafe and". Similarly, Yra commented, "I am emotionally distressed because of my experiences of having been bullied". Further, Donna remarked, "I have been insulted by my classmates."

Cultural differences and communication barriers. Students from different cultural backgrounds may face difficulties in adapting to the university environment and communicating effectively with peers and faculty. Cultural misunderstandings or communication barriers can lead to feelings and isolation and hinder the development of a sense of belonging and peace. This is affirmed by Gigi who stated, "I sometimes feel like an outsider because of my cultural group". Similarly, Hana mentioned, "I find it difficult to adjust

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to a new culture". Also, Erwin stated, "I find it difficult to understand other students' cultural practices and customs".

Conclusions

The Marian students manifest moderate sense of belongingness and peace in terms of valued competence, social acceptance, involvement

Sex and cultural affiliations do not affect the Marian students' sense of belongingness.

The Marian students' lived experiences of peace in the university show that Marians favor peaceful living environment and manifest these in their lives through their concept of peace, incorporation of peace into their daily interactions, and experiences in campus and creation of a peaceful environment at the university.

Challenges encountered by the Marian students greatly affect in their fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university .

Recommendations

1. Strengthen their sense of belongingness and peace through immersion activities and civic engagement.
2. Explore other variables that may surface other concepts on sense of belongingness and peace
3. Provide opportunities for Marian students to engage with diverse voices to gain a more comprehensive understanding of belongingness and peace.

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Informed Consent Form

Title of study and researchers **Harmony within: Nurturing Marians' lived experiences on belongingness and peace**

Name of researchers: Dr. Susan A. Galamay
Mr. Benyamin Messakaraeng (Primary collaborator)
Mr. Brian Baristo (Secondary collaborator)
Mr. Rogene Gonzales, Head, Research Department, PhilRights (External collaborator)

Organizational Affiliation: Saint Mary's University
School of Teacher Education and Humanities
Christian Faith Education Department

Introduction You are being invited by faculty researchers from Saint Mary's University to participate in their study entitled Harmony within: Nurturing Marians' lived experiences on belongingness and peace. You can take your time to decide whether to participate or not and you can ask questions any time for any word or concept in this form that you may not understand.

Purpose of the research The purpose of this study is to determine the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness at the university in general and when grouped according to their profile variables; explore how Marian students process their sense of belongingness and sense of peace in the university; identify the challenges encountered by the Marian students in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university; and craft programs that can be proposed to address and nurture the Marian students' sense of belongingness and peace in the university.

Type of intervention This study involves the use of survey questionnaire, interview guide questions, and focus group discussion. You are selected as a participant because you belong to the Marian community and it is assumed that you have rich experience as a Marian.

Participant Selection You are one of the 370 selected respondents. Please be informed that your participation is voluntary and you can withdraw anytime without explanation. Your non-participation and withdrawal will not affect your standing as a student. Should you choose to participate in the study, you shall be answering a questionnaire containing general demographic profile and items where you will reveal your

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Risk/benefit

level of sense of belongingness at the university, how you process your sense of belongingness and sense of peace, and the challenges you encountered in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university. Additionally, the questionnaire includes a survey test consisting of 20 items and interview guide questions. It is estimated that your participation in the study will not take more than 30 minutes. There is conflict of interest in conducting this study inasmuch as both the researchers and respondents of the study belong to Saint Mary's University. There is a potential risk of confidentiality breach for data that may be shared during the FGD since information sharing is between researchers and participants and among the participants. However, you will be contributing to the creation of new knowledge on students' belongingness and peace in the university as a result of this study and this may be beneficial not only in the academe but also to the community/society as a whole.

Payment/
Reimbursement
Voluntary participation

You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements.

Even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue and any information you have already provided will not be used in this study. Rest assured that your privacy will be respected and all answers will be respected and all your answers will be treated with confidentiality. The accomplished questionnaires will be retrieved only by the researchers, and your identity will be anonymized by providing you a number code instead of your name. The data you provided will be transferred to excel in number coded format. Except for the researchers no one will be able to identify you as respondent in this study. After the study is completed and finally bound, all the data will be deleted for good.

Sharing of results

The results of the study may be disseminated within Saint Mary's University through students' fora. Also, the study maybe submitted for publication in national or international journals. For any matter concerning this study, you can contact Susan A. Galamay through the following mobile number 0905 6266 411 or sgalamay@smu.edu.ph

Contact information

This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong

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Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

Certificate of Consent

This study is entitled Harmony within: Nurturing Marian's lived experiences on belongingness and peace. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of the Marian students' sense of belongingness at the university in general and when grouped according to their profile variables; explore how Marian students process their sense of belongingness and sense of peace in the university; identify the challenges encountered by the Marian students in fostering sense of belongingness and peace in the university; and craft programs that can be proposed to address and nurture the Marian students' sense of belongingness and peace in the university.

I have read the foregoing information. I had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to

Statement of the researcher or person taking the consent

Print name of participant

Signature of participant

Date: (MM/DD/YYYY)

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands that the following will be done:

1. S/he answers a questionnaire asking his/her demographic profile
2. She will answer the survey questionnaire and answer the interview guide questions

I confirm that the participant has been given the opportunity to ask questions and all his/her queries have been answered correctly to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily

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A copy of this informed consent form has been provided to the participant.

NAME and SIGNATURE

DATE

B. Interview guide questions

1. Reflective questions

- a. What does peace mean to you personally?
- b. How do you incorporate peace into your daily interactions and experiences on campus?
- c. In what ways do you create to creating a peaceful environment at the university?
- d. How do you handle conflicts or challenges in a peaceful manner within the university community?

2. Interpersonal connections

- a. How do you build relationships that promote understanding among diverse members of the university community?
- b. Have you experienced any moments of conflict resolution or mediation that led to a peaceful outcome?
- c. How do you support and uplift your peers to foster a sense of peace and unity in the campus?

3. Community engagement

- a. How does the university community promote a culture of peace and inclusivity?
- b. Are there specific events, initiatives, or programs at the university that resonate with your understanding of peace?
- c. In what ways can you actively participate in promoting peace and university within the university environment?

4. Personal growth and wellbeing

- a. How does cultivating a sense of peace contribute to your personal wellbeing and academic success?
- b. What self-care practices or routines do you engage in to maintain inner peace amidst the academic demands?
- c. How do you balance academic pursuits with activities that bring you a sense of peace and fulfillment?

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5. Impact and future aspirations

- a. How has your experience of peace at the university influences your personal growth and development?
- b. In what ways do you envision integrating the values of peace and harmony into your future endeavors beyond university life?
- c. How can your journey towards peace at the university inspire others and contribute to a more peaceful campus community?

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

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